

Review

Qigong as a Complementary Therapy for the Mental Health of Children and Adolescents: An Exploratory Narrative Review of the Evidence.

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Abstract: Background: Mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and behavioural disorders are increasingly prevalent in children and adolescents. Conventional treatments like pharmacotherapy and CBT have limitations, creating a need for complementary therapies. *Qigong*, an ancient practice rooted in Traditional Chinese Medicine, has shown promise in regulating the autonomic nervous system and improving mental health.

Objective: This narrative review examines the potential of *Qigong*, a traditional Chinese practice, as a complementary therapy for pediatric mental health.

Methods: A comprehensive search of major databases was conducted to identify studies on *Qigong* interventions for children and adolescents. Studies were included if they focused on mental health outcomes and involved *Qigong*.

Results: Eleven studies were included, consisting of 7 experimental studies and 4 systematic reviews. Findings indicate that *Qigong* can effectively reduce symptoms of anxiety, depression, ADHD, and other behavioural disorders. It may assist in managing autism spectrum disorder, Down syndrome, anorexia nervosa, and several other conditions. *Qigong* was particularly noted for regulating the autonomic nervous system and improving emotional regulation. *Qigong* interventions were well-received and showed minimal side effects.

Conclusion: *Qigong* shows promise as a safe and feasible complementary therapy for pediatric mental health. Further longitudinal, high-quality studies are necessary to validate these findings and optimise integration into clinical and educational settings.

Keywords: *Qigong*; Mental Health; Children; Adolescents.

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1. Introduction

Children's and adolescents' psychological development is shaped by the dynamic interplay between emotional, social, and physical health. In recent years, mental health conditions such as anxiety, depression, and behavioural dysregulation have increased alarmingly among youth populations¹⁻⁵.

Conventional approaches to the treatment of mental disorders in children and adolescents predominantly include pharmacotherapy and psychotherapeutic interventions, such as cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT). Pharmacological treatments, particularly the use of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), have demonstrated efficacy in managing symptoms of depression and anxiety; however, their use is frequently associated with adverse effects, including somatic complaints, behavioural activation, and an increased risk of suicidal ideation, especially in early stages of treatment^{6,7}. Psychotherapeutic methods like CBT have shown moderate to strong evidence of effectiveness across

a range of disorders; nonetheless, limitations persist regarding accessibility, high treatment costs, variability in therapist competence, and reduced effectiveness in complex or comorbid cases^{8,9}. These limitations highlight the critical need for the development and integration of complementary strategies that can address the heterogeneity of clinical presentations and improve long-term mental health outcomes in this population.

Ancient techniques with roots in Traditional Chinese Medicine, such as *Taijiquan* and *Qigong*, have become viable adjunctive therapy for mental health. Through regulated movement, breathing, and meditation, these methods, which fall under the category of Traditional Vegetative Biofeedback therapies, have been demonstrated to affect the regulation of the autonomic nervous system, promote homeostatic balance, and modify psychophysiological processes¹⁰⁻¹⁵. Through precise movements or postures, breathing methods, and meditation exercises, practitioners can alter biological functions and processes through self-directed applied psychophysiological feedback techniques¹⁶.

According to recent research, *Qigong* and *Taijiquan* may have a variety of positive effects on mental health^{11,17}. These interventions have been extensively examined in adults¹⁸⁻²³, but less so in pediatric populations. Nevertheless, recent evidence suggests their safety, feasibility, and possible efficacy¹¹.

This narrative review intends to consolidate existing research on the use of *Qigong* as an adjunct therapy for mental health in children and adolescents. Through the analysis of both experimental and systematic investigations, it aims to elucidate the therapeutic potential of these practices and recommend pathways for future interdisciplinary research and clinical incorporation.

2. Methods

2.1. Search Strategy

A comprehensive search strategy was developed to identify all relevant studies. Electronic searches were conducted in several major databases from their inception to January 2025.

The search strategy combined keywords and controlled vocabulary related to *Qigong*, Children and adolescents, and Mental Health. No language or publication date restrictions were applied initially, but limitations were noted and addressed during the screening process. We also manually searched the reference lists of included studies and relevant studies to identify additional eligible studies.

2.2. Study Selection

Two independent researchers screened the titles and abstracts of all identified records against the pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Studies deemed potentially eligible were retrieved in full text. The same two reviewers independently assessed the full-text articles for inclusion. Disagreements at both the title/abstract and full-text screening stages were resolved through discussion and consensus, or by involving a third reviewer when necessary.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Studies were included if participants were children or adolescents, investigated the intervention of *Qigong* and reported at least one mental health-related outcome.

Studies were excluded if they investigated interventions that were not related to *Qigong* or were in combination with interventions where the effect of *Qigong* could not be isolated. Chinese traditional exercises that were related to *Qigong* (eg. *Taijiquan*) were included when in combination with specific *Qigong* exercises.

2.4. Data Extraction

Data from the included studies were extracted independently by two reviewers using a standardised data extraction table. The form collected information on study characteristics such as author, year, study design, the studied condition, intervention and comparator details, outcome measures, and main results.

Any discrepancies during data extraction were resolved through discussion and consensus, with the involvement of the third reviewer if needed. Authors of primary studies were contacted for clarification or missing data when necessary.

3. Results and Discussion

The search strategy and consecutive screenings resulted in a total of 11 studies.

The included studies demonstrated significant heterogeneity, exploring various aspects of children's and adolescents' mental health and utilising diverse intervention techniques. To better synthesise the evidence within this context, our analysis comprised 7 experimental studies and 4 systematic reviews. The reviewed studies within the initially identified systematic reviews were excluded to avoid overlap and ensure a focused synthesis of primary and high-level evidence.

3.1. Experimental Studies

In Table 1, a summary of the included experimental studies is presented.

Table 1. Experimental studies' characteristics.

Title • Journal • Citation	Intervention	Groups	Outcome Measures
Effects of taijiquan and qigong practice over behavioural disorders in school-age children: A pilot study <i>Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies</i> Rodrigues et al. ²⁴	Yang-style TJQ 8-movement form BDJ QG	Intervention group only	ADHD, CD, ODD TRF - teachers Structured Interview - children
Taijiquan and qigong as a mindfulness cognitive-behavioural based therapy in the treatment of cothymia in school-age children - A preliminary study. <i>Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies</i> Rodrigues et al. ²⁵	Shao Yin Yang style TJQ 8-movement form (routine of the five animals) Shao Yin BDJ QG	Symptomatic group Asymptomatic group	Anxiety-depression (Cothymia) TRF - teachers
Assessment of Qigong Effects on Anxiety of High-school Students: A Randomized Controlled Trial <i>Advances in Mind-Body Medicine</i> Rodrigues et al. ¹⁶	Shao Yin QG (routine to calm and concentrate the Shen and regulate the heart)	QG group TV documentary group Typical school duties group	Anxiety STAI - students Salivary cortisol analysis - students
Xianggong (Fragrant Qigong) for the Health of School Children: A Qualitative Pilot Study of Feasibility and Effects. <i>Journal of Chinese Medicine</i> Witt et al. ²⁶	QG (Xianggong)	Only one intervention group per school	Quantitative assessments through Questionnaires for students, parents, and teachers, evaluating behaviour, school grades, absenteeism, quality of life, and health issues, alongside qualitative semi-structured interviews with teachers.
Qigong for Schoolchildren: A Pilot Study. <i>The Journal of alternative and complementary medicine.</i> Witt et al. ²⁷	QG (Xianggong)	One intervention group and one control group per school	Standardised questionnaires assessing complaints, concentration, creativity, grades, QoL, and social behaviour, along with teacher assessments and medical complaints documented by parents.

Group Qigong for Adolescents inpatients with Anorexia Nervosa: Incentives and Barriers. PLOS ONE Gueguen <i>et al.</i> ²⁸	QG exercises incorporating traditional forms such as White Tiger, Wild Goose, BDJ and Jade Body.	Intervention group only	Anorexia nervosa Semi-structured interviews Qualitative assessments of participants' experiences during and after QG sessions, their perceptions of body image, adherence to the practice, and the meaning attributed to QG, were analysed through IPA.
Improved speech following parent-delivered qigong massage in young children with Down syndrome: a pilot randomized controlled trial. Early Child Development and Care Silva <i>et al.</i> ²⁹	Parent-delivered QG massage	Intervention Group Control Group	Down syndrome Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development Raw scores

Abbreviations: TJQ - *Taijiquan*, QG - *Qigong*, ADHD - Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder, CD - Conduct Disorder, ODD - Oppositional Defiance Disorder, BDJ - Ba Duan Jin, TRF - Achenbach Teacher's Report Form, STAI - State-trait anxiety inventory, QoL - Quality of Life, IPA - Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis.

A 1-year pilot study in a school context with four children between 6 and 10 years old suggested that *Taijiquan* and *Qigong* might help regulate behavioural disorders such as attention-deficit hyperactive disorder (especially hyperactivity-impulsivity), oppositional defiant disorder, and conduct disorder ²⁴. The condition of positive vegetative behavioural patterns may be, in part, due to the characteristics of these techniques, acting on the nervous system and motivating a state of relaxation. Techniques such as these help address physiological symptoms of prolonged stress, regulating the mind and emotions ³⁰. In the study, the pathopsychophysiology of these behavioural disorders is discussed and theorised by the authors according to Chinese medicine.

Another 1-year preliminary study conducted with six school-aged children showed that these therapeutic approaches can be applied as a mindfulness cognitive-behavioural-based therapy with body movement in the treatment of anxiety-depression ²⁵. It demonstrated treatment capabilities in affected children, as well as preventive capabilities in children who did not display clinically relevant symptoms. In this article, the authors discuss and formulate a hypothesis about the formation of this condition based on the theory of the five internal pathologic agents of Chinese medicine. Parallelism is made between this theory and several psychological and medical formulations, such as the theory of emotions, the gut-brain axis, and the tryptophan metabolism.

Furthermore, a six-week randomised controlled trial with 104 high-school students was carried out to assess *Qigong's* effects on anxiety ¹⁶. The *Qigong* group was the only group to achieve a statistically significant improvement in both state and trait anxiety. Improvement was mostly observed in male participants. Regarding the biochemical assessment, salivary cortisol changes were not significant, however, a higher tendency for improvement was observed in the *Qigong* group, which may result in significant changes if the intervention period was longer.

A six-month qualitative pilot study ²⁶ conducted in four Berlin schools involving 140 children aged 10 to 17 years suggested that Xianggong (Fragrant *Qigong*), a simplified form of traditional *Qigong*, may support the psychosocial and physical well-being of schoolchildren. According to teacher reports, the practice was associated with reductions in restlessness, aggression, and social tension while promoting calmness, focus, and a sense of classroom community. Children also reported improved sleep, vitality, and fewer physical complaints such as allergies and colds. These outcomes may be partially attributed to the regulatory effects of *Qigong* on the autonomic nervous system, fostering a relaxed physiological state. In this study, the feasibility and integration of Xianggong

within regular school lessons were also explored, with findings highlighting both excessively easy exercises leading to a lack of concentration, time constraints within the school schedule and parental scepticism due to the perceived cultural or spiritual origins of *Qigong*.

Similarly, another six-month preliminary study²⁷ involving 90 school-aged children investigated the integration of Xianggong into regular classroom settings as a means to promote behavioural and emotional regulation. The intervention was associated with improvements in social behaviour and emotional balance, particularly in reducing restlessness and enhancing classroom harmony, as reported by teachers. Additionally, some students showed improvements in physical well-being, such as better sleep and fewer allergy-related symptoms. The study combined quantitative and qualitative methods, highlighting the utility of *Qigong* both as a preventive and supportive strategy in school health. In this article, the authors emphasise the relevance of integrating traditional mind-body techniques into modern educational settings, drawing attention to the psychosomatic and regulatory potential of *Qigong* based on Traditional Chinese Medicine theory.

A qualitative study²⁸ involving sixteen adolescent girls hospitalised for anorexia nervosa investigated the integration of *Qigong* as a complementary intervention within a multidisciplinary treatment program. The findings suggested that *Qigong* might support emotional regulation, enhance body awareness, and facilitate non-verbal emotional expression in this clinical population. Participants described the experience as calming and grounding, with some reporting improvements in anxiety, emotional tension, and bodily reconnection. These outcomes may be partially attributed to the physiological mechanisms of *Qigong*, which promote parasympathetic activation and support embodied awareness. Such techniques may counteract the hyperaroused stress states commonly observed in individuals with anorexia nervosa. In this article, the authors explore how *Qigong* practice aligns with Chinese medical theory, particularly the regulation of Qi and the balance of internal organ systems implicated in emotional and somatic dysregulation.

Finally, a five-month pilot randomised controlled trial²⁹ involving children with Down syndrome investigated the effects of parent-delivered *Qigong* massage on expressive language development. The intervention demonstrated a significant improvement in expressive language skills among children in the treatment group compared to controls. The positive outcomes may be partially attributed to the somatosensory and regulatory effects of *Qigong* massage, which targets the autonomic nervous system and promotes relaxation, sensory integration, and body awareness. These mechanisms may support neurological pathways involved in speech production and auditory processing. In this article, the authors explore the therapeutic potential of *Qigong* massage for developmental delays and hypothesise its role in enhancing communication through physiological and energetic modulation consistent with the principles of Chinese medicine.

3.2. Systematic Review Studies

Table 2 summarises the systematic reviews included in this study.

Table 2. Characteristics of the included systematic reviews.

Title • Journal • Citation	Number of included studies	Intervention(s)
Effects of Tai Chi and Qigong in Children and Adolescent: A Systematic Review of Trials. Research Reviews Riskowski et al. ³¹	13	TJQ (Yang-style or Chen style) QG variations like 18-posture QG or Peace Power QG.
Qigong in the treatment of children with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review <i>Journal of Integrative Medicine</i>	10	QG massage Nei Yang Gong

Rodrigues et al. ³²		
The Therapeutic Potential of Five Animal Qigong (Wu Qin Xi) for the Wellbeing of Children: A Systematic Review. Integrative and Complementary Therapies.	8	Wu Qin Xi or Five Animal QG (tiger, deer, bear, monkey, and bird)
Rodrigues et al. ³³		
The Effects of Tai Chi and Qigong Exercise on Psychological Status in Adolescents: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. Frontiers in Psychology.	10	TJQ (Chen-style), mindfulness-based TJQ QG: Turo Qi training, BDJ, Laughing QG, and Xianggong.
Liu et al. ³⁴		

Abbreviations: QG – *Qigong*, TJQ – *Taijiquan*, BDJ – Ba Duan Jin.

A systematic review to identify *Qigong* interventions was carried out, focusing on the effects on children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder ³². Results demonstrated that *Qigong* seems to decrease significantly the severity of sensory, behavioural, and language impact of this neurodevelopmental disorder. *Qigong* also showed to improve self-control, sensory and cognitive awareness, healthy physical behaviour as well as sociability. Favorably, it was also observed an increase in child-to-parent bonding and a decrease in parenting stress which is important for a long-term parent-delivered treatment.

Another systematic review ³³ was conducted to examine the effects of Wu Qin Xi, a traditional form of Five Animal *Qigong*, that mimics the movements and postures of the five animals, on the well-being of children. Results demonstrated that Wu Qin Xi appears to significantly improve multiple aspects of children's health, including psychological outcomes such as reduced stress and anxiety levels, as well as enhanced cognitive functions like memory and executive performance. The practice also showed benefits for physical health, particularly in improving respiratory function in children with asthma and pneumonia and promoting better posture, spinal mobility, flexibility, and body composition. Among children with autism spectrum disorder, Wu Qin Xi contributed to improvements in behaviour, sensory integration, and social interaction. Collectively, these findings suggest that Wu Qin Xi may serve as an effective complementary intervention for supporting the integrated development and well-being of children.

One more systematic review and meta-analysis was carried out to evaluate Tai Chi and *Qigong* interventions targeting adolescents, focusing on their effects on psychological outcomes such as anxiety, depression, and stress ³⁴. Results demonstrated that these mind-body practices appear to significantly reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, with *Qigong* showing particularly strong effects. Additionally, *Qigong* was associated with a significant decrease in cortisol levels, indicating a potential physiological benefit in managing stress. However, the interventions showed no consistent improvements in perceived stress, mood, or self-esteem. These findings suggest that Tai Chi and especially *Qigong* may serve as effective therapeutic modalities to support adolescents' psychological well-being.

4. Final remarks

This narrative review has explored the potential role of *Qigong* as an adjunct therapy in the mental health care of children and adolescents, highlighting its growing relevance in addressing complex psychological and emotional challenges. The studies examined indicate that *Qigong*, alongside more conventional treatment modalities like pharmacotherapy and CBT, presents a promising option for enhancing mental health in young populations.

Several key findings emerged from the analysis of both experimental and systematic studies.

Across all the included studies, *Qigong* demonstrated a strong safety profile and was well-accepted by children and adolescents. This suggests that, when integrated thoughtfully into existing treatment protocols, *Qigong* can provide a low-risk intervention with minimal side effects, making it a viable option for patients, particularly those who may experience adverse effects from pharmacological treatments.

As well, *Qigong* interventions were shown to be effective in addressing a wide range of mental health symptoms, from anxiety and depression to behavioural disorders such as ADHD and conduct disorder, and a wide range of neuropsychiatric illnesses. This aligns with previous evidence in adult populations, extending its therapeutic benefits to younger demographics. In particular, *Qigong*'s ability to regulate the autonomic nervous system, foster relaxation, and promote emotional regulation makes it a valuable complementary treatment for managing stress and anxiety-related disorders.

A key mechanism through which *Qigong* operates seems to be the regulation of the autonomic nervous system, fostering a balance between sympathetic and parasympathetic activity. This has profound implications for treating conditions like anxiety, depression, and stress, as these disorders are often marked by autonomic dysregulation. Furthermore, the mind-body connection facilitated by *Qigong* encourages self-awareness and mindfulness, enhancing the child's ability to cope with emotional dysregulation and promoting resilience.

An important aspect of the reviewed studies is the incorporation of *Qigong* within school environments. These techniques have shown promise in improving classroom behaviour, focus, and emotional regulation, suggesting that *Qigong* could be an effective strategy for enhancing mental health support within schools. This integration could reduce the stigma associated with mental health treatments and promote a holistic approach to child development, focusing not just on academic achievement but also on emotional and social growth.

Despite the encouraging findings, much remains to be explored. The research so far has been largely exploratory, with few large-scale, longitudinal studies in pediatric populations. Future research should focus on the long-term efficacy of *Qigong* interventions, especially in populations with more complex or comorbid mental health conditions. Additionally, understanding the optimal dosage, frequency, and duration of *Qigong* practices in younger patients will be critical for determining best practice guidelines. Further interdisciplinary research involving child psychologists, paediatricians, and traditional medicine experts will help to fine-tune these approaches and provide more definitive recommendations for clinical use.

5. Conclusions

Qigong represents a valuable and underutilised tool in the growing toolkit for treating mental health disorders in children and adolescents. Its combination of physical movement, mindful breathing, and meditative practices not only addresses the psychological symptoms but also fosters overall well-being, aligning with holistic principles that integrate mind, body, and spirit. As research continues to uncover its therapeutic potential, *Qigong* may emerge as a cornerstone in pediatric mental health care, complementing existing treatments and offering a holistic path forward for children and adolescents facing mental health challenges.

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